

A Reproduction Study for “A Framework for Analyzing the Impact of Missing Data in Predictive Models” by F. Santore et al.

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ABSTRACT

We evaluate the reproducibility of the paper “A framework for analysing the impact of missing data in predictive models” by F. Santore et al. [5] published in the Short Paper Track of the 2020 CIKM conference. In the paper, the authors explored the effect of different aspects concerning the data structure on the accuracy of a logistic model. Therefore, they described a simulation study, which artificially generated data with configurable parameters, for example sample size, number of input variables, correlation between input variables and distribution of the variables. With the simulation study’s results, the authors constructed a data set containing the parameter values and the measured accuracies and fit a multiple linear regression model.

The paper provides a link to a repository of all the functions used in the simulation of the data. Building on these resources, we examine the reproducibility of the paper. Additionally, we describe obstacles we have encountered and problems in the supplied code.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Information systems → Incomplete data.

KEYWORDS

data sets, incomplete data, reproducibility

1 INTRODUCTION

Missing data is a problem encountered in many statistical and machine learning applications. The most common methods of treating missing values are imputation and complete case analysis. All of the methods of dealing with missingness may introduce bias. The paper claims, that “it is hard to verify the effectiveness of [...] imputation techniques and their impact on data analysis” and focuses only on removing missing records.

The investigated paper designs a study with controlled parameters and performs a systematic analysis on the resulting accuracies for the full and incomplete data sets. As the final step, the results are evaluated in a multiple linear regression model.

The variable parameters, which the study describes are

- sample size ($n = 500, 1000, 1000$)
- number of explanatory variables ($p = 10, 50, 200$)
- type of explanatory variables (Binom($p=0.5, n=1$), Pois(10), $N(0, 1)$)
- correlation between explanatory variables ($\rho = 0, 0.5, 0.8$)
- predictive power of input variables on the target variable ($\alpha = 0.2, 0.5, 0.8$)
- percentage of records with missingness (10% or 30%)
- correlation of missingness pattern

- repetition of each setting, chosen as $k = 150$

Barring the number of repetitions, this results in 486 parameter combinations. Each of these settings is said to be repeated k times, such that the inner quartile range of the measured accuracies can be computed for the plot.

2 DATA

2.1 Experimental Setup

As mentioned above, the experiment deals with different factors that are changed, in order to measure a factor level’s effect on the accuracy of the resulting model. We are using a full factorial design, meaning we assess several model accuracies for each combination of the factors.

The experiment uses an R[3] script and the R-libraries stats[4], SimCorMultRes[6], caret[1] and bindata[2]. None of the used version numbers are known. We repeated the experiments with R version 4.0.2 (2020-06-22). The package versions were 4.0.2 for stats, 1.7.0 for SimCorMultRes, 6.0.86 for caret and 0.9.19 for bindata.

2.1.1 Generate Explanatory Variables. First, the function `generate_predictors(n, j, dist, rho)` is called. This function returns a $n \times j$ matrix of random vectors with marginal distribution `dist` and correlation matrix

$$(\rho_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } i=j \\ \text{rho} & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

2.1.2 Generate Response Variable and Regression Coefficient. The generation of the target variable and the regression coefficients are more involved: through simulations, a multiplicative factor called *effect size* needs to be determined. This ensures that the input variables have a predictive power of α . The regression coefficients are then generated, using a geometric distribution with parameter α . The response variable is then simulated by a binomial distribution based on the logistic model.

2.1.3 Impose Missingness. In the two previous steps, a complete data set and a response variable was created. Next, we want to impose all three missingness mechanism, therefore the function `missing(data, q, t, r)` is called. It takes a data matrix `data` as generated in 2.1.1, a proportion of missingness q , a string `t` specifying the missingness mechanism and a correlation parameter r . There are four different mechanisms for missingness:

- “missing completely at random” (MCAR), where the probability for an observation to be missing is the same for all observations,

Figure 1: First and third accuracy quantiles

- “missing at random” (MAR), where the missingness pattern is related to another variable,
- “missing not at random” (MNAR), here the missingness of the variable depends on the variable itself or
- complete (COM), this is the type of the original data set.

2.1.4 Build Model and measure Accuracy. Each data set is split into 70% training and 30% test data using `caret`’s `createDataPartition`. Only the target variable is supplied to the function, and it tries to balance the class distributions within the splits.

The model is built with `glm` from the package `stats`. If given an input with missing data, the incomplete rows are dropped. The test set is then predicted with the trained model and a confusion matrix is built. As a last step, the accuracy is computed based on the confusion matrix.

2.2 Problems with the Pipeline

2.2.1 Correlation between binomial variables. The paper claimed to produce data sets with a correlation matrix specified by the user. In

the repository, this was realized through the function `rnorta` from `SimCorMultRes`. The desired correlation matrix was of the form described in (Equation 1). Unless the variables were supposed to be uncorrelated, for the binomial distribution, we always observed a lower correlation. In table 1, the results of a test of 100 generated predictors with 10 variables and 500 observations are shown. Though the correlation ρ was specified, the measured correlations r had a mean which was much lower than that.

Table 1: Entered correlation ρ vs. measured correlation: r

ρ	mean(r)	sd(r)
0.5	0.333	0.017
0.8	0.588	0.019

2.2.2 Correlation matrix of MNAR missingness. The paper claimed to impose a block structure on the correlation matrix of the missingness indicator matrix M in the case of MNAR. In actuality, the

correlation structure is a toeplitz matrix with off-diagonal entries 0.5 and 0.8 like

$$(\rho_{ij}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } i = j \\ 0.8 & \text{for } |i - j| \leq \lfloor p/2 \rfloor \\ 0.5 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

For $p \times p$ matrices of this form with $p \geq 10$, this is no positive definite matrix and cannot be used to describe a covariance structure.

2.2.3 Complete Case Analysis of the Accuracy. In the case of missing data, the test sets, too, had missing values. The paper did not describe, how missing values were treated in this case, but an analysis of the source code revealed the following:

The accuracy of the predictions was computed with `caret`’s `confusionMatrix` function, after the true values and the predictions were transformed to binary factors. Internally, this function calls `base-R`’s `table` function, which drops entries of the same position from the vectors, if either of them are NA.

While the accuracy of a model would be computed as the number of correct predictions divided by the number of all predictions, for the incomplete data sets, the number of predictions is smaller than the number of observations, given that any missing value records are dropped.

2.2.4 Computed repetitions. In the analysis of the provided code, we noticed that the repetitions were realized through two nested loops. The outer loop, which is repeated 10 times, constructs a set of predictors, and the inner while-loop constructs a response vector, the data sets with missing values and computes a training- and test-partition in each repetition. A failure to reset the inner loop’s index variable back to 0 after each iteration of the outer loop, means, that the total number of repetitions is only 15.

3 MODIFICATIONS OF THE PIPELINE

In order to reproduce the results presented by the authors, we analyzed the code thoroughly. In general, the code is commented moderately well, i.e. sufficient to understand what each function is trying to do. The functions provided are running, but there is no code running the simulation for all factor combinations at the end. Since the code that we needed to reproduce the paper was working, we set our main goal to be the improvement of the run time, as the original code by the authors could easily be made faster. Lots of loops and slow functions were used in the original code that could simply be exchanged with quicker alternatives. Additionally, there were a lot of statistical measures computed, that were not used for any further explorations, hence we cut them out of the code. This way, we were able to improve the run time for the simulation of the same factor combination from about four hours to around 30 minutes. To make the code run out of the box, we added a function that will run the simulation for every factor combination, and then store the results in the global environment, as well as save a CSV-file for every simulation run, so they can easily be located.

In our pipeline, we have the following steps:

- (1) Run `simulation_final.R`, which is a script, that automatically generates all simulation results and saves each combination in a CSV file.

- (2) Merge all results into one data set, we have provided our results in `accuraciesMerged.csv`.
- (3) Interpret the parameter settings as factor variables and build a multiple linear regression model, explaining the measured accuracies. Our code is provided in `solve_linear_model.R`.

Table 2: Parameter estimates and standard error

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error
(Intercept)	0.898	0.001
NINPUT_500	-0.009	0.001
CINPUT_0.5	0.001	0.001
CINPUT_0.8	-0.003	0.001
TINPUT_Poisson	-0.006	0.001
TINPUT_Gauss	-0.005	0.001
PPINPUT_0.5	-0.001	0.001
PPINPUT_0.8	0.002	0.001
TMD_MCAR	-0.003	0.001
TMD_MAR	-0.003	0.001
TMD_MNAR	-0.005	0.001

4 RESULTS

After much consideration, and due to time constraints, we decided to simulate fewer data sets, i.e. not recompute all of the parameter combinations. Therefore, the number of input variables was fixed at 10, and we only looked at data sets with a sample size of 500 and 1000. Furthermore, we only looked at a percentage of 30 percent missing data values. While we did improve the run time of the code significantly, it still did not seem feasible to us to finish all the simulations, as run time rapidly increases with increasing number of input variables and increasing sample size.

Figure 1 shows all of our results for accuracy quartiles from our simulations. Since we did not use the exact same parameter combinations as were depicted in the original paper’s plot, our results differ a lot from what the authors presented in their paper. Still, even for the simulations that overlap with the paper’s and use the same parameters, the resulting accuracies look a lot different. The accuracies derived from our simulations do not vary a lot among the different parameter settings, while the original paper claims that the range of parameters leads to very different accuracy outcomes. However, we did find one conclusion to match the claims of the original paper: that with increasing sample size, the precision of the accuracy goes up, i.e. the bars in the plot are narrower. All of the accuracies calculated by our simulation gather around values of about 0.9, which is generally an approximate result to the author’s outcome. Note that the authors only included the results for a correlation of 0.8 between the input variables, which does not allow us to compare our additional results with what they concluded.

Lastly, we use the results of our simulations to estimate how the varying factors affect the model accuracy, by fitting a linear model. For this, the authors did not present any code in the repository. Given the results from the original data, we believe the model considered all of the parameter values as factors and used a contrast treatment to encode them. Table 2 compares the outcome of the original paper to the ones we obtained. Note that we did not use

exactly the same factor levels for all of the factors used in the original paper, so our results are different naturally. We observed that the chosen parameter have little to no effect on the accuracy of the model. This contradicts the results published by the authors, where they found most of the parameters, except predictive power and correlation between input variables, to have a relatively large effect on the accuracy of a model.

5 CONCLUSION

The paper does a decent job explaining every step that is needed to reproduce the findings. The code that is provided is certainly very helpful to reproduce the paper, though not sufficient. The given code was only able to generate accuracies according to the input parameters given. We added a function that runs simulation for all factor combinations and returns the first and third accuracy quartiles computed. Moreover, we added the code to fit the linear model, estimating the effect each parameter has on the accuracy. Additionally we needed to make some major alterations in order to improve the performance, as well as fix some errors within the

code. All in all we think it was moderately easy to reproduce the paper “A Framework for Analyzing the Impact of Missing Data in Predictive Models” by F. Santore et al., though our findings overall were not consistent with the ones presented in the original paper.

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